

CORPUS-BASED STUDY OF THE STRUCTURE OF VERB PHRASES IN GRADE 7 LITERARY TEXTS

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ABSTRACT

Verb phrases in literary texts have different patterns or structures that are crucial in the construction of sentences. This study aimed to identify the structure of the verb phrases in grade 7 literary texts, specifically on the auxiliary and main verb combinations, to analyze whether those literary texts matched with the MELC in English 7 about phrases and tenses. Involving a linguistic analysis of corpus, it was a qualitative study. The primary source of this study was the ninety literary texts taken from Grade 7 English books currently used by DepEd and private. This study followed four steps: data preparation, familiarization, coding, and merging and working with all data. This study described the frequency of auxiliary and main verb combinations used from the corpus. The result of the analysis showed that there were 11 auxiliary and main verb combinations in the corpus of literary texts. Thus, the modal auxiliary + main verb, the perfect auxiliary + main verb, the progressive auxiliary + main verb, and the passive auxiliary + main verb combinations were the most frequently used verb phrases. Based on the concordance lines of verb phrases in the corpus, verb phrases are always used as verbs in the sentences. The results revealed that the past perfect tense was the most used tense in grade 7 literary texts, suggesting that the choice of literary texts in grade 7 aligned with the MELC in English 7. A learning activity sheet was developed to support and promote students' learning about verb phrases.

Keywords: *auxiliary verbs, corpus-based study, literary text, main verbs, tenses, verb phrases*

INTRODUCTION

Language users have pragma-semantic knowledge linked to specific grammatical constructions, like knowing a great deal about what kinds of semantic meanings and functions constructions have and what sorts of pragmatic effects one

can generate (Linell, 2009). They should know that particular syntactic forms or constructions carry particular meanings (Kaschak & Glenberg, 2000). For example, the subject cannot be followed directly by the object or other noun phrase; the verb must come between them in an English sentence (Fodor, 1995).

Although not all parts of speech are used in every sentence, every sentence must have a verb. It is the name given to the parts-of-speech class in which most of the words express actions, processes, and the like, which is an essential part of a complete sentence (Schachter & Shopen, 1985; VERBS, 2004). Verbs are essential in English syntactic construction because there would be no grammatical construction without them. Thus, verbs are possibly the most essential lexical and syntactic category because all English sentences must contain at least one verb. They provide the relational and semantic framework in a sentence (Fellbaum, 1990).

Grammar can be divided into two parts: The syntax is concerned with how words combine to make phrases, clauses, and sentences, whereas morphology is concerned with how words are formed. The word, which is also important in the lexicon, phonology, and graphology, is given special prominence in this division (Huddleston & Pullum (2005).

The verb structure can be one or more words like phrases. A phrase is the grouping of one or more words that together achieve the role that a single word might express in other conditions (Morley, 2000). Likewise, it is a set of words forming a unit consisting of a head or 'nucleus' and other words or word groups clustering around it. If the head is a verb, the phrase is a verb phrase (Reed & Cappelle, 2008). A verb phrase is any combination of auxiliary verb, also known as a helping verb, and the main verb. What differs from a verb phrase from a verb is that a verb is just a word that can be an action verb or a linking verb, and a verb phrase is a group of words that can be different combinations of auxiliary verb and action verb, which means it is more than one word. But even if a verb phrase has more than one word, it functions as the verb in a sentence. Verb phrases form tenses besides present and past tense, including progressive tenses and perfect tenses. They also demonstrate the sentence's mood, intention, and other information.

Furthermore, English grammar has dramatically increased (Palmer, 2014). However, because the verb, or the verb phrase, is central to the sentence structure, no syntactic analysis can proceed without careful consideration of it; thus, there have been more books and articles about verbs than nouns and any other class of words. Besides, maturational limitations, difficulty in detecting the conceptual components of verbs, difficulty in learning which semantic features enter into verbs and how they combine, and order of information are why verbs lag behind nouns in early acquisition (Gentner, 2006).

Recent work by Halimi (2017) concludes that English teachers must comprehend the English verb phrase competently since, in English clause structure, the verb phrase realizes the function of the verb element.

Verb phrases were identified from a corpus of literary texts in the English 7 textbooks, which were instantly generated using a corpus-linguistic software that can automatically search terms that occurred most frequently in the compiled corpus.

These words were shown on a computer screen in order of decreasing frequency of occurrence, which the first word displayed had the most number of incidents in the corpus.

The researcher decided what linguistic analysis would be made depending on her line of interest in the identified structure of verb phrases. She chose a structural analysis of the different combinations of verb phrases in literary texts. With a corpus-based study, corpora which generally consists of thousands or even millions of words that are representative samples of a particular type of naturally occurring language, can therefore be used as a standard reference with which language can be measured (Baker, 2006).

The researcher's primary purpose of the study was to identify the structure of the verb phrase in literary texts from Grade 7 textbooks to analyze whether the literary texts in those textbooks matched with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in English 7 that are closely related to this study. Because although the Covid19 pandemic halted the use of textbooks, the activities in the self-learning modules (SLMs) are taken from the textbooks that are based on the streamlined competencies from the K to 12 Curriculum Guide known as MELCs. Hence, this study aimed to develop a Learning Activity Sheet about the structure of verb phrases to cater to students' needs in Distance Learning during this pandemic. Accordingly, this study will guide students on how they could easily spot the verb in sentences with the auxiliary verb and main verb combination that could guide them in understanding tenses or what meaning they have expressed in sentences.

Verb Structure

A verb phrase refers to a phrase composed of maybe at least one verb and its other dependents (Van Valin, 2000), such as the objects, complements, and other modifiers, excluding the subject (Majid, 2015). However, some linguistic works use the term 'verb phrase' as described by the latter. In contrast, others use it in a much narrower sense to denote no more than the main verb and any auxiliaries accompanying it (Reed & Cappelle, 2008). When the two principal parts of a verb, such as the present participle and the past participle, are used as verbs in sentences and helping verbs are used with them, they are called verb phrases (Carroll et al., 2001).

A verb has four main parts: present, present participle, past, and past participle (Carroll et al., 2001). It has three types: action verbs, linking verbs, and helping verbs which are also called auxiliary verbs (VERBS, 2004). The purpose of the auxiliary verbs is to help main verbs to accomplish specific functions; thus, an auxiliary verb needs a partner, whereas a main verb does not (Master, 1996). They help other verbs to form verb phrases (Carroll et al., 2001). The auxiliary verbs have little or no lexical meaning. Hence, they are 'helper' verbs in that they help form complex verb forms that express either a grammatical notion like passive, progressive, or tense or one or more modal ideas and their meanings are more schematic and more abstract (Reed & Cappelle, 2008). Nelson & Wowk (2012) support the latter's view by pointing out that 'English is not a heavily inflected language. Instead, it uses helping verbs with grammatical functions in subject-verb combinations without adding semantic meanings to the sentences in which they are found.

Additionally, an auxiliary verb determines the mood or tense of another verb in a phrase by conveying that the action will take place in the future (Betti, 2021). The primary auxiliaries are those "be" verbs: be, is, was, were, are, am, been, and being, the have verbs such as have, has, and had, and the do verbs: do, does, and did (Mack, 2015). It is important to note that the "be" verb is the most common and the most irregular verb in English (Carroll et al., 2001). In 2001, Popescu discussed that primary auxiliaries are what make up the analytical forms of the English verb. They could be the marks of grammatical specifications: tense, aspect, tempo-aspectuality, mood, voice, and verbal forms (interrogative, negative, and interrogative negative). She further states that the "be" verb as an auxiliary can occur in two different patterns. First, with the present participle of the full verbs to express aspectuality (e.g., Miriam is learning Arabian.) The second is to express actively or passively with the main verb in the past participle (e.g., Madonna has been awarded lots of prizes.) The "have" verb as an auxiliary verb is the mark of perfectivity that is either simply used or in combination with progressive or modality. For example, (a) She has just finished the translation., (b) You will have been working in this office for two years by the end of this month., (c) She may have said the truth, but I doubt it. In addition, the do verb, when used as an auxiliary verb, is a mark of the interrogative, and when used with the negation not, it is a mark of the negative. Thus, with its role as an auxiliary verb, it is used in yes/no questions (e.g., Do they work?) and in special questions in the simple present and simple past tense (e.g., How did they start their business?)."

Another kind of auxiliary verb is a modal verb. Modals are units of surface structure that evaluate only the actions that a human being intends to realize (Kakzhanova, 2013). Modal verbs have simple forms, but a wide variety of semantic connotations and communicative functions that can generally be related to scale ranging from possibility may to necessity must (LI, 2017). Can, could, will, would, may, might, shall, should, and must are the nine core or central modal verbs (Oktavianti & Ardianti, 2019; Rizvić-Eminović & Šukalić, 2019). Concerning their semantic and syntactic features, modal verbs do not need inflections to indicate tense, person, voice, etc." Likewise, modals express the certainty, possibility, or necessity of a planned action being realized, and they have no morphological verb characteristics such as aspect, voice, tense, mood, number, and person (Kakzhanova, 2013). To be more specific, can, could, may, might express possibility, permission, and ability; shall, should, must express necessity and obligation; and will and would express volition and prediction (Oktavianti & Ardianti, 2019). Further, because modal verbs are auxiliary verbs, they have to be used along with the main verb, not on their own (Betti, 2021). Out of those nine core modal verbs, would is the most frequently used in fiction and spoken genre and the least used in the Academic genre (Rizvić-Eminović & Šukalić, 2019).

Concerning the structure of the verb phrase, there is one fundamental principle that each auxiliary determines the inflectional form of the following verb. The rules in verb phrase constructions in English can be summarized as follows: for modal auxiliary, the verb that follows is in the base form, for perfect auxiliary, the verb that follows is in the -en form, for progressive, the verb that follows is in the -ing form, and for the passive, it is in the -en form (Halimi, 2017). Additionally, the sixteen possibilities of verb phrase combinations, regardless of the differences in the choice of modal, are as follows: main verb (e.g., takes), "passive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., is taken), "progressive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., is taking), "progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., is being taken), "perfect auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., has

taken), "perfect auxiliary + passive auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., has been taken), "progressive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., has been taking), "perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary verb + main verb" (e.g., has been being taken), "modal auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., may take), "modal auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., may be taken), "modal auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., may be taking), "modal auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g. may be being taken), "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., may have taken), "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., may have been taken), "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., may have been taking), and "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" (e.g., may have been being taken) (Halimi, 2017). In cases when there are several auxiliaries in a verb phrase, an adverb may be placed after the first one (Hernández, 2006). Adverbs may occur after an auxiliary verb (White, 1991).

However, there are only four common verb phrase patterns: "modal auxiliary + main verb," "perfect auxiliary + main verb in past participle," "progressive auxiliary + main verb in -ing," and "passive auxiliary + main verb in the past participle" (Justice & Ezell, 2008).

The "passive auxiliary + main verb combination" may express the passive voice of the verb, which is always constructed with a form of the verb "to be" and the past participle of another verb (a verb ending in -d, -ed, -n, -en, or -t) (Fordyce-Ruff, 2012). The passive voice can be identified by searching for a specific verb (Ramm et al., 2017) and can be used when what was done is more important than the doer of the action (Flauta, 2006). For example: (a) It is reported., (b) It was reported.

Second, the "progressive auxiliary + main verb" combination may form the present progressive and past progressive tense (Hughes, 2001). The principal part of the main verb ends in -ing (Carroll et al., 2001). To form the present progressive, am/is/are + verb-ing is the pattern or am/is/are + not + verb-ing for negative statements and for the past progressive, the pattern is was /were + verb-ing or was /were + not + verb-ing for negative statement (Uchiyama, 2006). For example: (a) She is talking.; (b) He was taking a break.

Third, the "perfect auxiliary + main verb" combination forms the present perfect tense and past perfect tense. The present perfect tense is formed with the "auxiliary has/have + the past participle" (Emmerson, 2006). "Have" is always an auxiliary when it marks perfect tense, where it usually occurs with a following past participle (Huddleston, Pullum, & Reynolds 2021). These are some sample sentences of the present perfect tense: (a) She has visited me.; (b) We have received grocery supplies. The underlined verbs are in the present perfect tense in the given examples. It refers to 'past with present relevance,' or 'past involving the present' (Leech, 2014). For past perfect tense, it is composed of two parts: the past tense of the verb "to have" (had) + the past participle of the main verb (Hughes, 2001). These are some sample sentences of the past perfect tense: (a) I had invited him.; (b) We had informed them about the case. The underlined verbs are in the past perfect tense in the given examples. This tense has the meaning of past-in-the-past, or more accurately, 'a time further in the past, seen from the viewpoint of a definite point of time already in the past (Leech, 2014).

Lastly, the "modal auxiliary + main verb" combination may form the simple future tense when the modal verb is "will." The verb "will" is the normal auxiliary for the future, including its negative construction "won't" as its variant form because "will" is at least ten times more frequent than shall (Leech, 2014). The simple future tense is composed of will + simple form (Uchiyama, 2006). These are some sample sentences of the simple future tense: (a) I will go there.; (b) I will visit you there. The underlined verbs are in the simple future tense in the given examples.

Further, the other verb phrase combinations: the "progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" combination, will form the passive progressive tense where the auxiliary "be" combines with the progressive auxiliary being, which indicates that it commonly occurs with a present or past tense auxiliary (Hundt & Smith, 2009). The passive present progressive tense follows the pattern am, is, or are + being + past participle (Pamungkas, n.d.) For example: (a) I am being invited.; (b) I was being invited.

The "perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" combination will form the present perfect progressive tense and past perfect progressive tense. These tenses start with the relevant part of the verb "to have" followed by "been" and end with the main verb + ing (Fordyce-Ruff, 2012). For example: (a) I have been waiting for you., (b) I had been studying for three hours.

Next, the "perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" combination may form the passive present perfect progressive tense, which may follow the pattern: "has/ have/had + been + being + the past participle" (Halimi, 2017). Also, the "perfect auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" combination may form the passive present perfect (has, have + been + past participle) and past perfect (had + been + past participle) (Jeffrey, 2015).

Then, the "modal auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" combination may form the simple future passive tense with the "will be + past participle" pattern (Jeffrey, 2015).

Another combination, "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + main verb," may form the future perfect tense, which is made up of combining the simple future of the verb to have (will have) + the past participle of the main verb (Hughes, 2001; Uchiyama, 2006). For example, (a) I will have left.; (b) He will have taken everything.

The "modal auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" combination may form the future progressive tense, which is composed of a combination of two elements: the simple future of the verb 'to be' + the present participle (base+ing) (Hughes, 2001) or will + be + verb-ing (Uchiyama, 2006). For example, (a) Antonette will be baking a cake.; (b) We will be celebrating if this project works.

Furthermore, the "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" combination follows the pattern: "modal auxiliary + have + been + past participle (verb in -en)", and the "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" combination follows the pattern: "modal auxiliary + have + been + present participle (verb in -ing)" (Halimi, 2017).

The verb phrase internal structure is the auxiliary system + the main verb. The main verb functions as the bearer of the semantic content of the verb phrase and

establish the different relations with all the other elements in the sentence (Rodríguez-Navarro, 1984). Moreover, students learn language structure by using linguistic forms in specific settings provided by the teacher (Sampson, 1981).

Based on the literature review, the researcher found out that verb phrases come in different structures that should be carefully analyzed because they would suggest different meanings in a text. Moreover, since there are various verb phrase patterns, the researcher grasped the need to study the patterns of the different auxiliary and main verb combinations using a corpus of literary texts. Also, the researcher wanted to find out what might the verb phrase combinations in literary texts usually express. Hence, this study is proposed to focus on the verb phrase structure in grade 7 literary texts.

Research Questions

The study aimed to identify the structure of the verb phrases in grade 7 literary texts. Specifically, the study sought answer the following research questions:

1. What auxiliary and main verb combinations occur in the corpus?
2. How shall a learning activity sheet be developed to enhance students' knowledge of verb phrases?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Qualitative research analyzes data from direct fieldwork observations, in-depth, open-ended interviews, and written documents (Patton 2005). Similarly, according to Braun & Clarke (2013), the most basic definition of qualitative research is that it uses words as data are collected and analyzed. Moreover, they emphasize that qualitative research refers to data collection techniques or analysis and a wider framework for conducting research or paradigm.

The structural analysis focuses on the relations between units instead of trying to sort units into categories defined by the inner attributes of these units (Hibbeler & Kiang 2015). Brill (1993) states that part of a person's knowledge of language consists of knowing how to assign an abstract structural description to sentences like the awareness of the word and phrase classes of a language, the members of each class, and the relationships that hold between class. This study employed structural analysis as it analyzed qualitatively each word that makes up the structure of a verb phrase to determine its meaning. Corpus linguistics is concerned with understanding how individuals use language in various contexts. In corpus research, one common method used is to look at the environment of a particular word or phrase to see what other words are found with the reference of the word (Crawford & Csomay 2015). Thus, the study employed the corpus-based approach in analyzing the structure and tense of verb phrases.

Source of Language Data

The study used a corpus of 90 literary texts from grade 7 English books currently used by DepEd and private schools. The study used the books used private schools and not only the book from DepEd because the results of this study will benefit both public and private school Grade 7 students and English teachers. Table 1 presents the texts that compose the corpus.

Table 1
Composition of the Corpus

Type of Text	Number of Texts	Number of Tokens
Short story	53	95,388
Essay	10	9,232
Epic	5	5,485
Legend	7	4,912
Fable	6	2,591
Folktale	6	2,223
Myth	3	1,210
Total	90	121,041

Table 1 presents the source of language data of this study culled out from the literary texts from the Grade 7 English book used by DepEd and four books used by private schools: English Learner's Material 7 (DepEd) coded as DE, Proficiency in English (REX) coded as RX, English Communication Arts and Skills through Philippine Literature (PHOENIX) coded as PH, English Across Continents (DIWA) coded as DW and Roads to Greatness (SIBAL) as SB.

The corpus was composed of short stories, narrative essays, epics, legends, fables, folktales, and myths. There were 50 short stories with 95,388 words, ten essays with 9,232 words, five epics with 5,485, 7 legends with 4,912 words, six fables with 2,591 words, six folktales with 2,223 words, and three myths with 1,210 words. Summing up, there were 121,041 words in these genres.

Research Instrument

The main instrument in this qualitative study was the researcher. In analyzing the verb phrase structure, the researcher used Antconc software to generate the different types of Grade 7 literary texts from DepEd and private schools. Anthony (2005) describes AntConc as a freeware, multi-platform, multi-purpose corpus analysis toolkit designed by him for specific use in the classroom. One of AntConc's features includes a powerful concordancer, word and keyword frequency generators,

tools for cluster and lexical bundle analysis, and a word distribution plot. Second, it offers the choice of simple wildcard searches or powerful regular expression searches and has an extremely easy-to-use, intuitive interface. Besides, the most straightforward analysis available when users use AntConc is the frequency list, which can help them see which words and forms are being used more often in a corpus. Thus, the frequency list gives users indications of grammar at the word level, which they may wish to investigate further.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering phase of this study started with identifying 90 literary texts from grade 7 English textbooks used by public and private schools. The choice of the book and texts included in the corpus was based on the fact that the researcher has previously taught grade 7 English, where her students had poor reading comprehension on the texts of the book that she and her students were using. Aside from that, she also wanted to explore the private schools' textbooks.

After identifying the ninety literary texts to be included in the corpus, the researcher classified the ninety literary texts as short story, essay, epic, legend, fable, folktale, and myth. Then, she coded short story as SO, essay as ESO, Epic as EO, legend as LO, Fable as FAO, folktale as FO, and myth as MO. After that, she scanned all the texts using the Goggle lens and copied the plain texts to Google docs. Next, each corpus underwent the weeding out process to have a smooth flow in the running in the AntConc software. In the weeding out process, the researcher excluded the signs, symbols, or punctuation marks that the software does not recognize, like apostrophe ('), apostrophe in s ('s), and quotation marks (" "). Each corpus was converted to plain text in a single folder to run or process the data using the software after the weeding process. Hence, the coded literary texts were run in the software: SO1 was the first short story, and SO53 was the last short story. ESO1 was the first essay, and ESO10 was the last essay; EO1 was the first epic, and EO5 was the last epic; LO1 was the first legend, and LO7 was the last legend; FAO1 was the first fable, and FAO6 was the last fable, and MO1 was the first myth, and MO3 was the last myth. Finally, the researcher looked for all the auxiliary verbs that were used for analysis. The list of coded literary texts was in Appendix C.

Data Analysis

In qualitative research, data analysis is a creative process. As the data analysis instrument, the researcher explores and reflects on the meaning of the data (Jacelon & O'Dell, 2005). And to create good research findings, the analysis must give results that are meaningful to the individuals for whom they are intended and described in the language they understand (LeCompte, 2000).

The study followed the general steps to analyze qualitative data.

According to Ruona (2005), the first step in the analysis process of qualitative data is data preparation. During this stage, the researcher gathered descriptive data coming from the corpus of 90 literary texts from English 7 textbooks, which were stored in a table.

The second step was familiarization. In this step, the researcher reviewed the purpose of the study and the research questions that the study wanted to find out. The researcher looked for the frequency of occurrence of verb phrases in the corpus.

The third step is coding. In this step, the researcher needed to know the corpus's auxiliary verb and main verb combinations. To have a focus on the auxiliary verb and main combinations, the researcher selected all “have”, “be,” and modal auxiliary verbs.

The last step is merging and working with all data to generate meaning. During this stage of the analysis process, the researcher compared the results with the existing knowledge or finished studies that are reviewed and reflected in Chapter2- Review of Literature- are to be. The researcher presented if the results are congruent or counter to existing knowledge or information.

RESULTS

Table 2 presents the frequency of occurrence of auxiliary and main verb combinations in the corpus.

Table 2

Frequency of Occurrence of Auxiliary and Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus

Auxiliary and Main Verb Combinations	Frequency
Modal Auxiliary + Main Verb	1, 281
Perfect Auxiliary + Main Verb	693
Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb	452
Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb	387
Perfect Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb	81
Modal Auxiliary + Perfect Auxiliary + Main Verb	77
Modal Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb	67
Perfect Auxiliary + Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb	29
Modal Auxiliary + Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb	17
Progressive Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb	9
Modal Auxiliary + Perfect Auxiliary + Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb	1
Total	3, 094

Table 3*Frequency of Occurrence of Modal Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus*

Modal Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations	Frequency	Example
would + main verb	378	would be, would go
could + main verb	291	could bend, could build
will + main verb	211	will build, will act
can + main verb	142	can put, can give
must + main verb	74	must have, must fight
shall + main verb	55	shall return, shall accept
should + main verb	49	should like, should be
may + main verb	44	may beat, may give
might + main verb	37	might find, might cut
Total	1, 281	

Table 4*Frequency of Occurrence of Perfect Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus*

Perfect Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations	Frequency	Example
had + main verb	545	had planted, had begun
have + main verb	100	have been, have ended
has + main verb	48	has become, has ended
Total	693	

Table 5*Frequency of Occurrence of Progressive Auxiliary+ Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus*

Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb	Frequency	Example
was + main verb	277	was embroidering, was buzzing
were + main verb	93	were attracting, were doing
are + main verb	45	Are becoming, are going
is + main verb	19	is growing, is lying
am + main verb	18	am going, am guarding
	1968	

Total 452

Table 6

Frequency of Occurrence of Passive Auxiliary+ Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus

Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb	Frequency	Example
was + main verb	240	was painted, was arranged
were + main verb	99	were added, were covered
is + main verb	30	is considered, is crowned
are + main verb	17	are called, are made
am + main verb	1	am filled
Total	387	

Table 7

Frequency of Occurrence of Perfect Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus

Perfect Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb	Frequency	Example
had + been + main verb	55	had been pierced
has + been + main verb	10	has been allowed
have + been + main verb	3	have been sent
Total	81	

Table 8

Frequency of Occurrence of Modal Auxiliary + Perfect Auxiliary + Main Verb Combination in the Corpus

Modal Auxiliary + Perfect Auxiliary + Main Verb	Frequency	Example
would + have + main verb	28	would be assigned
could + have + main verb	15	could have been
must + have + main verb	14	must have been

should + have + main verb	13	should have thought
might + have + main verb	5	might have forgotten
may + have main verb	1	may have helped
shall + have + main verb	1	shall have come
Total	77	

Table 9

Frequency of Occurrence of Modal Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus

Modal Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb	Frequency	Example
could + be + main verb	18	could be heard
would + be + main verb	16	would be brought
can + be + main verb	10	can be overcome
will + be + main verb	8	will be called
must + be + main verb	4	must be removed
should + be + main verb	4	should be transferred
may + be + main verb	3	may be called
might + be + main verb	2	might be caught
shall + be + main verb	2	shall be rewarded
Total	67	

Table 10

Frequency of Occurrence of Perfect Auxiliary + Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus

Perfect Auxiliary + Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb	Frequency	Example
had + been + main verb	18	had been carrying
have + been + main verb	9	have been watching

has + been + main verb	2	has been associating
Total	29	

Table 11

Frequency of Occurrence of Modal Auxiliary + Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus

Modal Auxiliary + Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb	Frequency	Example
will + be + main verb	7	will be building
would + be + main verb	7	would be betraying
could + be + main verb	4	must be getting
must + be + main verb	2	could be wooing
Total	20	

Table 12

Frequency of Occurrence of Progressive Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb Combinations in the Corpus

Progressive Auxiliary + Passive Auxiliary + Main Verb	Frequency	Example
was + being + main verb	6	was being fixed
were + being + main verb	3	were being consumed
Total	9	

DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 2, eleven auxiliary and main verb combinations were used in the corpus. However, the "modal auxiliary + main verb" combination had the highest frequency among the twelve combinations with the frequency of 1, 281 occurrences in the corpus. It must be noted that the "modal auxiliary + main verb" has been the common combination among the 90 corpora in the English 7 textbooks because of its greater gap with the other combinations.

The "perfect auxiliary + main verb" combination was the second-highest, with a frequency of 693. Then, the third-highest frequency was the "progressive + main verb" combination with 452 occurrences in the corpus. The fourth one was the "passive + main verb" combination which had a frequency of 387. The fifth one was the "perfect

auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" combination, which has a frequency of 81. The sixth one is the "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + main verb," with a frequency of 77 in the corpus.

Next are the combinations of "modal auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" combination with 67 occurrences, "perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" with the frequency of 29, "modal auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" with the frequency of 17, and the "progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb" with the frequency of 9. Lastly, the "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" combinations had the lowest frequency of 1 in the occurrences of the corpus. These were the eleven auxiliary and main verb combinations used with 3, 094 total occurrences in the corpus.

This implies that the two-verb combinations are the most common patterns of verb phrases in literary texts. The combination of "modal auxiliary + main verb" had the highest frequency regardless of the modal used because modal verbs have to be used along with the main verb, not on their own (Betti, 2021). It also proves the discussion of Justice & Ezell in 2008 that there are only four common patterns of a verb phrase. These are the "modal auxiliary + main verb," "perfect auxiliary + main verb in past participle," "progressive auxiliary + main verb in -ing," and "passive auxiliary + main verb in the past participle." Moreover, of the possibilities of verb phrases with the auxiliary verb and main verb combinations (Hallimi, 2017), four were not used in the corpus. These are the four-verb combinations: "modal auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb," "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb," and modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb which is a five-verb combination. Also, it implies that in the delivery of instruction for a grammar lesson or Communicative Language Teaching about the verb phrase structure, the literary texts used in this study may be used as springboard.

Table 3 reveals that nine modal auxiliaries were used to combine main verbs; because modal verbs are auxiliary verbs, they have to be used along with the main verb, not on their own (Betti, 2021). The modal would + main verb had the highest frequency of occurrences among the nine combinations with the frequency of 378. The second highest was the modal could + main verb with the frequency of 291. The third highest was the modal will + main verb with the frequency of 211. The fourth was the modal can + main verb with the frequency of 142. It was respectively followed by the modal must + main verb with the frequency of 74, modal shall + main verb with the frequency of 55, the modal should + main verb with the frequency of 49, the modal may + main verb with the frequency of 44, and lastly, the modal might + main verb with the frequency of 37.

This implies that all nine core modal verbs were used in the corpus together with the main verbs. Out of those nine core modal verbs, would was the most frequently used, which affirms Rizvić-Eminović & Šukalić's investigation in 2019 that *would* is the most frequently used modal in fiction and spoken genre.

As illustrated in Table 4, the three perfect auxiliaries were used in grade 7 literary texts to combine with main verbs. The "had + main verb" combination had the

highest frequency of occurrences with the frequency of 545 occurrences which had a remarkable distance between "have + main verb" with the frequency of 100 and "has + main verb" with the frequency of 48. This indicates that the past participle of the perfect auxiliary was the most frequently used perfect auxiliary in grade 7 literary texts. Thus, the past perfect tense was the most commonly used perfect tense in those literary texts.

As shown in Table 5, five be verbs such as was, were, are, is, and am were used as progressive auxiliaries combined with the main verbs in the present participle. "Was + main verb" had the highest frequency of occurrences in the corpus with the frequency of 277. It was followed respectively by "were + main verb" with the frequency of 93, "are + main verb" with the frequency of 45, "is + main verb" with the frequency of 19, and "am + main verb" with the frequency of 18. With the past participle of the "be" verb as the most commonly used progressive auxiliary verb combined with the main verb, it can be noted that the past progressive tense is more frequently used than the present progressive tense.

As illustrated in Table 6, five be verbs were used, such as was, were, are, is, and am, just like in the previous table, as passive auxiliaries combined with the main verbs. The combination with the highest frequency was "was + main verb" with 240 occurrences. Then, the second highest was "were + main verb," with the frequency of 99 occurrences, which is quite far from the latter. Next was "is + main verb" with the frequency of 30, "are + main verb" with the frequency of 17, and "am + main verb" which occurred only once.

As revealed in Table 7, there were three-verb combinations with the perfect auxiliary as the first auxiliary verb and been as the second auxiliary verb added with the main verb. Regarding the frequency of occurrences, had + been + main verb was the highest with the frequency of 55. It was followed by "has + been + main verb" with the frequency of 10 and have + been + main verb with the frequency of 3. Therefore, the past perfect auxiliary was the most frequently used in the grade 7 literary texts, just like in the previous verb phrase combinations with the perfect auxiliary. Additionally, been consistently comes after the present or past perfect auxiliary and before the main verb in three-verb phrase combinations.

As shown in Table 8, there were three-verb combinations with modals as the first auxiliary verbs followed by present perfect auxiliary verbs and main verbs in the past participle. "Would + have + main verb" combination had the highest frequency of 28 occurrences. Then, it was followed by these combinations: "could + have + main verb" with the frequency of 15, "must + have + main verb" with 14 occurrences, "should + have + main verb" with the frequency of 13, "might + have + main verb" with the frequency of 5, and "may + have + main verb" and "shall + have + main verb" that equally occurred once in the corpus. This indicates that not all nine core modal verbs were used as the first auxiliary verb in the three-verb combinations in the corpus, and the other modals did not frequently occur as well.

Table 9 shows that there were three-verb combinations wherein all nine core modal verbs were used as the first auxiliary verb followed by "be" as the second auxiliary verb and the main verb in the past participle. "Could + be + main verb" combination had the highest frequency of occurrences in the corpus with the frequency

of 18 and closely followed by "would + be + main verb" with the frequency of 16. Then, "can + be + main verb" followed with the frequency of 10, "will + be + main verb" and "should + be + main verb" combinations with an equal frequency of 4, "may + be + main verb" combination with the frequency of 3, and "might + be + main verb" and "shall + be + main verb" which similarly occurred twice. This implies that the passive future tense is seldomly used in grade 7 literary texts and the three-verb phrase combinations with modals as the first auxiliary verbs.

As illustrated in Table 10, there were three-verb combinations with the perfect auxiliary as the first auxiliary, "been" as the second auxiliary, and the main verb in the present participle. Out of the total 29 frequency of occurrences of the perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb combinations in the corpus, had + been + main verb had the highest frequency with 18 occurrences. It was followed by have + been + main verb with the frequency of 9 and has + been + main verb with two occurrences. This shows that the present perfect progressive tense was more seldomly used than the past perfect progressive tense in the corpus.

As revealed in Table 11, there were three-verb combinations with modal verbs as the first auxiliary verb, "be" as the second auxiliary verb, and the main verb in the present participle, which had 20 occurrences. In those occurrences, "will + be + main verb" and "would + be + main verb" combinations similarly occurred 18 times in the corpus. "Could + be + main verb" combination occurred four times, and the "must + be + main verb" combination occurred twice in the corpus. This indicates that although there were occurrences of the future progressive tense in the corpus, they were seldomly used.

As shown in Table 12, there were three-verb combinations with 9 occurrences. The first auxiliary verb was a "be" verb. The second auxiliary was another "be" verb, "being," and the main auxiliary verb in the present participle. "Was + being + main verb" combination had the frequency of 6, which was only half higher than the "were + being + main verb" combination with the frequency of 3. It can be noted that only the past be verbs were present in the corpus. This indicates that only passive past progressive tense seldomly occurred and no passive present progressive tense in the corpus.

Modal Auxiliary + Perfect Auxiliary + Progressive Auxiliary + Main Verb

The "modal auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" combination may form the future progressive tense, which is made up of two elements: the simple future of the verb 'to be' + the present participle (base+ing) (Hughes, 2001) or will + be + verb-ing (Uchiyama, 2006).

In the corpus, the "modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb" combination, a four-verb combination, only occurred once in the corpus. It was "must + have + been + main verb" in the present participle wherein there were three auxiliary verbs: "must" as the first auxiliary, "have" as the second auxiliary, "been" as the third auxiliary. It indicates that the corpus's most seldomly used verb phrase is the four-verb combination.

Implications

This study shows language teachers that the literary texts in grade 7 textbooks used by DepEd and private schools aligned with the MELCs in English 7. With this, teachers might consider utilizing the textbooks used in their school and the other school's textbooks for grade 7 English when teaching about the past and past perfect tenses included in the MELCs. To better understand the two tenses mentioned, they might also consider providing more activities about the structure of verb phrases when unpacking the "use phrases, clauses, and sentences appropriately and meaningfully (EN7G-II-a-1)" MELC. Hence, they may focus their discussion and activities on the "past perfect auxiliary + main verb" that expressed past perfect tense and "past passive auxiliary + main verb" that expressed past tense.

Conclusions

The following is the summary of findings on the structure of the verb phrases in grade 7 literary texts.

1. What auxiliary and main verb combinations occur in the corpus?

Based on the analysis made from the corpus of grade 7 literary texts, there were 11 auxiliary and main verb combinations. From the corpus analysis, the modal auxiliary + main verb had the highest frequency. The perfect auxiliary + main verb had the second-highest frequency. It was followed by progressive auxiliary + main verb and passive auxiliary + main verb. Hence, the seldomly used auxiliary and main verb combinations are the three-verb combinations: the perfect auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb, modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + main verb, modal auxiliary + passive auxiliary + main verb, perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb, and modal auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb. Whereas the modal auxiliary + perfect auxiliary + progressive auxiliary + main verb, a four-verb combination was the most seldomly used verb phrase structure as shown in Table 2.

2. How shall a learning activity sheet be developed to enhance students' knowledge of verb phrases?

The researcher developed a Learning Activity Sheet (LAS) on the MELC, "Use phrases, clauses, and sentences appropriately and meaningfully" (EN7G-II-a-1). As a supplement assessment tool, learning activity sheets can be used by teachers to understand students' previous knowledge, learning outcomes, and learning process. They can also be used to allow students to keep track of their learning progress while they are on distance learning modality. As stipulated in DepEd Order no. 012, s. 2020, Modular Distance Learning involves individualized instruction that allows learners to use SLMs in print or digital format, whichever is applicable in the learner's context, and other learning resources like learner's materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides, and other study materials. Since there is no prescribed format for SLM or a learning activity sheet, it would be safe to adhere to the Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) Learning Resource Standards published last May 8, 2020, which has the following elements: introduction/learning objectives labeled as What I Need to Know, pretest as What I Know, review as What's In, activity 1 as What's New, discussion of activity 1 as What is It, enrichment activities as What's More, generalization as What I Have Learned, application as What I Can Do, Assessment, and Additional Activities.

However, in the developed learning activity sheet, the objectives are not labeled as What I Need to Know, there is no review or What's In, and there are no additional activities. Moreover, the activities in the LAS were anchored on the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach, which would allow the learners to explore the language even without the presence of the teacher and collaborative activities.

In the corpus of grade 7 literary texts, the auxiliary and main verb combinations or verb phrase structures were two-verb combinations, three-verb combinations, and four-verb combinations. The two-verb combinations of the three verb phrase structures that occurred the most were modal auxiliary + main verb, perfect auxiliary + main verb, progressive auxiliary + main verb, and passive auxiliary + main verb.

Generally, the results of the study revealed that the past perfect tense was the most used tense in grade 7 literary texts because the first auxiliary verbs in the most frequently used auxiliary verb and main verb combinations are in the past tense, and narrative texts use past tense. It would suggest that the choice of literary texts in grade 7 aligned with the MELC in English 7, "use the past and past perfect tenses correctly in varied contexts." In teaching this competency, a Learning Activity Sheet anchored on the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach was developed to help students develop their higher-order thinking skills, such as asking them to construct sentences using the verb phrase structure based on real-life contexts or situations.

Recommendations

The researcher made the following recommendations based on the constructed conclusion:

1. Students who have difficulty identifying verbs in sentences with two-verb combinations, particularly in the tenses of the verb formed by those combinations, may use this study.
2. Module writers are encouraged to provide more activities on the "past perfect auxiliary + main verb" that expressed past perfect tense and "past passive auxiliary + main verb" that expressed past tense.
3. For effective grammar and language teaching, Grade 7 English teachers are encouraged to utilize the sentences taken from the Grade 7 literary texts in providing examples and activities to students in teaching verb phrases.
4. Future linguistics researchers are encouraged to use the result of this research as a supplement to their existing knowledge or as a starting point for new research employing other corpora to conduct corpus-based analysis to teach the other MELCs in English effectively.
5. Copies of this study may be shared with the language teachers to encourage them to develop more effective Learning Activity Sheets to enhance students' knowledge about verb phrases and other grammar lessons.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical considerations that were observed in the study are the following.

Acknowledgment of Works of Other Authors. The researcher's data was gathered using literary texts from DepEd and private school English Grade 7 textbooks. When collecting the corpus, the researcher acknowledged and recognized by stating the title and publisher of each textbook utilized in the data collection process. The textbooks' title and publication company were found in the study's source of language and coded in the Appendix C. Also, using the APA referencing system, works of other authors used in the study were acknowledged.

Data Conformity. The researcher ensured that the use of data from online sources conformed to the standards stated by the data provider.

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